

Tengku Fakinah (D. 1933) Indonesia's Woman Ulama

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ABSTRACT

This study discusses the da'wah contribution of Indonesian female ulama Tengku Fakinah (d. 1933 AD). This research uses qualitative methods by making and observing works, books, academic research, videos, internet sources, and historical documents. The existing data is then analyzed using the explanatory analysis method where the logic of social phenomena is common sense by using historical, anthropological, and sociological approaches. This research tries to show the role model of female ulama Tengku Fakinah so that women today can learn and imitate the activities and struggles of these female ulama so that many benefits are generated for the improvement of the ummah, especially women. The concept of women scholars, contributions, strategies carried out by these women scholars are presented. Then the supporting and inhibiting factors of women ulama in preaching are also discussed so that they can be understood in depth.

INTRODUCTION

History records that apart from male clerics, there are also female ulemas with the capacity and influence in society. However, their existence did not develop any further, like the existence of male clerics. As a result, the spread of Islam to various places in the world, including in Indonesia, was carried out by male clerics. Then when Indonesia became independent, the ulama became a kind of authority attached to men only. Meanwhile, female clerics do not get enough proportions in public areas, affecting many people. On the other hand, the position and role of ulama since independence until now have been more dominant in the hands of men.

Although in Islamic teachings such as in Surah An-Nahl verse 97, Annisa verse 124, Al-Ahzab verse 35 shows the equality of degrees between women and men in the sight of Allah and only piety makes the difference in the sight of Allah; the dignity of women in Islam where: Human civilization will not continue without women, women have given birth to humanity both men and women, and respect for women is the command of Allah and His Messenger; however, women must be knowledgeable because the degree of a man or woman, if he believes and has knowledge will be much higher than a man or woman who believes but does not try to study. In the verses of the Qur'an we also find many texts that encourage women to learn knowledge. Not only the knowledge of the hereafter but also the knowledge of the world. Even women at the time of the Prophet SAW did not only take care of household affairs. They were also active in other activities outside the home. In fact, it has become a daily profession. However, the condition of the majority of patriarchal-based societies positions men as the center of socio-cultural construction so that social problems arise that affect various aspects of human life. And by gender activists and feminists. so that in various aspects related to women, positioning women unequally.

Women in Islam are also elevated by the presence of the Prophet Muhammad with Islamic law. So to position women who also have good dignity, women are required to improve their social conditions by having good knowledge. With the knowledge of women, their condition will automatically be better and they can even reach the position of authority as men. In Indonesia, the patriarchal culture also has an impact on the condition of women. The anxiety of many circles about the ulama scarcity in Indonesia is allegedly due to the religio-sociological construction that focuses on the ulama's concept. In the context of Indonesia, expertise in the field of fiqh alone cannot be called an ulama. Many people in Indonesia are experts in this field but are not yet seen as ulama. There is a contradictory definition; people active in socio-religious activities such as assemblies of taklim to the provision of prayers are called ulama. Often people have little knowledge but are still seen as scholars because they have pesantren. And this debate is still heating up as the dynamics of the ummah's development. They are thirsty for the needs of Islamic teachings but are presented with increasingly diverse choices.

Moreover, with the development of new media (internet), the claims of the clergy are increasingly undirected. And if we look at female figures who have

clerical status, the convenience of social media as a source of da'wah content encourages the emergence of "Millennial Ustadzah." The rise of the appearance of Nyai, ustadzah, dā'iyah, influencers, and students and students in the Muslim community on internet-based social media also helps the presence of women as actors of da'wah and also what the general public calls women clerics. However, in this study, the assumption of the inexistence of female scholars due to patriarchal traditions cannot be fully justified because this study shows that great women who hold the status of ulama can still show their existence as scholars in the community as well as male scholars. It's just that because of the nature of women who are more in the domestic sphere, only a few women can become scholars compared to the percentage of men who become scholars. In fact, the ulemas of these women were also recognized by the community in their time. As specifically emphasized in 3 (three) verses, namely: QS. Ali Imran in verse 195, QS. an-Nisa in verse 124 and QS. an-Nahl in verse 97; all three hint at the concept of ideal gender equality and provide assertion that individual achievements, both in the spiritual field and professional careers, do not have to be dominated by one gender alone.

Because the relationship between men and women is a relationship that complements each other. Both have their own weaknesses and strengths. All men and women cannot be equalized. Everyone is competing to be the best. However, in this race, they should not corner or demean each other. All of them have the same point and provision. The focus of the goal in this race is to reach the degree of taqwa in His sight. Interestingly, besides not being allowed to discredit or subordinate women or men, this race is helping and working together. For this reason, maintaining good relations between men is highlighted by the Qur'an when describing the creation of humans. More specifically, to maintain silaturahmi between each other. Suppose we look more deeply; before Indonesia's independence, female ulama appeared and initiated efforts to strengthen Islamic, humanitarian, and national values through the struggle against the colonialists and the development of education for women. As in Aceh, there is Sultanah Sri Ratu Tajul Alam Syafiuddin Johan Sovereign (1612-1675), a brilliant and active person in developing science. During her reign (1644-1675), science and literature flourished. There is also Siti Aisyah Wetin We Tenrille (d. 1919) from South Sulawesi, a female scientist specializing in government and literature, author of the Epos La-Galigo, which reaches 7,000 folio pages, and the founder of the first modern education for men and women in Ternate.

Cut Nyak Din (d. 1908) and Cut Meutia (1870-1910) from Aceh, women fighters against the Dutch in the Aceh war. The struggle continued with Raden Ajeng Kartini (1879-1904), a student of KH. Sholeh Darat (1820-1903) from Semarang was an intelligent woman pioneer of the Indonesian women's movement. There was Dewi Sartika (1884-1947) from Bandung (wife of Raden Kanduruan Agah Suriawinata, administrator of Sakola Istri Bandung), founder of Sakola Istri (1904), which later turned into Sakola Kautamaan Istri (1910), a place for women to learn and practice skills. Make handicrafts typical of Bandung. Another female cleric was Nyai Siti Walidah (1872-1946), the wife of

KH. Ahmad Dahlan (1868-1923), from Yogyakarta. She and her husband pioneered education for women, such as Sopo Tresno (1914), Wal-'Ashri, and the Maghreeb School, which was the embryo of the founding of Aisyiyah.. Nyai Walidah's clerical capacity posited her being invited by ulama in Solo to present her efforts to pioneer women's education in front of male clerics. Furthermore, there was Rahmah El Yunusiah (1900-1969) from Padang Panjang, a pioneer in Islamic women's education and a freedom fighter. Rahmah studied with several scholars and aspired to improve the position of women through modern education based on religious principles. Rahmah also founded the Padang Panjang Putri Diniyah School.

And far away if we look around the 18th-19th centuries there was a female scholar who preached among women in her time. It's just that because there is little literature that raises her, understanding about her is very difficult to examine. Moreover, there is limited information about the female ulama. She is Fatimah Al-Banjari (d. 1828 AD). This ulama deserves to be discussed and recognized because there are works produced but her work is not published on her behalf due to the strong patriarchal tradition in her time. Based on the above explanation, this article tries to examine and answer How is the contribution of da'wah made by Fatimah Al-Banjari (d. 1828 AD)? and How is the da'wah strategy, supporting and inhibiting factors in da'wah?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ulama

The ulama comes from the word 'alima-ya'lamu-'ilman (people with deep, broad, and steady knowledge). In the Qur'an, there are two words of ulama, namely in Surah Fatir verse 28 and Surah al-Shu'ara' verse 197. The term ulama itself is the plural form of the Arabic noun (fa'il) 'alim, derived from the verb 'alima, which means "to know" or "to know about." While 'alim is someone who has the attribute of 'ilm as a force firmly rooted in science, someone who is highly educated in science and literature. In short, the ulama are the owners of 'ilm. 'Alim is one of the attributes of Allah (asmaul-husna), means as All-Knowing. In the Qur'an there is a verse that is formulated with a question sentence: *يَعْلَمُونَ لَا وَالَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُونَ الَّذِينَ يَسْتَوِي هَلْ قُلٌّ* "Is it the same between those who know and those who do not know?" (QS. Az-Zumar: 9). Sentences of questions like this are known in the science of interpretation as "questions that deny": it means "Those who know are not the same as those who do not know". The words of the ulama are stated in the letter Fatir verses 27-28. Ulama, in the context of the verse, are people who understand and study the laws of life in the universe. Ulama are an elite layer in the structure of Islamic society. He has a critical role in the socio-cultural setting of the Muslim community, both Sunni and Shia traditions. The position of the ulama in this society is strengthened by theological texts that confirm the ulama as heirs of the prophet.

In the Qur'an, many other words have the same meaning or connotation as ulama. Including ulul 'ilmi (who has knowledge), ulil abshar (who knows), ulin nuha (who has common sense), ulul albab (who has a heart or core/substantive knowledge, and ahludz dhikr (who always mentions and remembers God). All the abovementioned words are often translated or

identified with scientists, scholars, intellectuals, and others. The terminology of ulama in the context of Indonesian culture is a title given to people who are considered to understand and understand Islamic religious sciences. Ulama are also agents of social change. This is usually evidenced by a person's ability to read the Qur'an and the yellow books. With their expertise in religious scholarship, ulama are also often understood as religious leaders or figures. In the traditions of Indonesian society or the archipelago, especially in Java, someone who understands the religious sciences is more familiarly called a kiai. And when referred to, the original word kiai also has a different connotation. Because in the palace tradition, the title of kiai (called Pak Yai) is usually assigned to someone who has certain spiritual skills. Ulama are also impressed as people who are diligent in worship, read a lot of the Qur'an, make remembrance, and are good at praying. They become a reference in all matters relating to religion, including giving fatwas. The terminology has, of course, reduced the genuine meaning of the ulama. Apart from the above terminological debate, however, the ulama have a special position in society.

The strategic roles and functions of ulama can be summarized as: 1) Ulama are the Heirs of the Prophets, 2) The presence of ulamas is a blessing, 3) Ulamas are Guides, Builders, and Guardians of the Ummah, 4) the ulama is the Controller of the Rulers, 5) Ulama are the Source of Knowledge, 6) Ulamas have a fear of Allah, 7) Looking at the Ummah with a Compassionate View, 8) Ulama as a thinker, 9) Ulama as organizers, 10) Mautul Alim, Mautul Alam. Islam prohibits discrimination against matters concerning humanity. The difference between men and women is not an essential but a functional difference. Thus, loving God is the same as loving equality because, in principle, Islam is rahmatal Lil Alamin which does not discriminate between one another.

Woman Ulama

In Arabic, there are no equivalent mu'annats (female). The term "Ulama" can refer to either a man or a woman. So, in essence, ulama are irrelevant if they are only identified with men; women can also be called ulama. If it is associated with the term 'ulama,' then a female ulema is a woman who has a depth of knowledge in the fields of religion, humanities, society, and nature. In the perspective of KUPI, "women clerics" have deep knowledge, a fear of God (integrity), a noble personality, uphold justice, and provide benefit to the universe. Women Ulama refers to women who become ulama, the same as women entrepreneurs or women writers. Meanwhile, the Women's Ulama showed focus, study, and, most importantly, the perspective of the Ulama, who always paid attention to justice for women and minority groups. With this explanation, it is easy to understand that Female Ulama does not have to be female, while Women Ulama may not have a proper perspective on women. Appreciation of the world's female scholars, legitimacy for their roles, and identification of lessons learned from various Islamic countries on Islamic issues, women's rights, issues of violence, radicalism, and world peace.

Canonization, the transmission of books, and changes in the definition of "ulama" have also eroded the contribution of women to Islamic treasures. Is it

not enough for only male scholars? Male clerics are less able to study Islamic laws and other religious matters, so there is a need for female clerics. Because there are many things about women that men cannot explain, only women themselves are representative to explain them, like the problem of various kinds of blood issued by women. Of course, this explanation would be more precise if a woman explained it. Al-Sakhawi (d. 1497 AD) also noted that there were 1075 prominent women, 405 of whom were prominent hadith and fiqh experts. Ibn Hajar (d. 1449 AD) recorded 191 women, 168 of whom were professors of hadith and fiqh.

The Kitab Al-Thabaqat-Kubra contains 4,250 entries of early Islamic figures up to the third century Hijri. Of these, 629 female characters were written. This number is significant, considering that finding female characters is not very easy. In another book, Kitab Al-Dhaw 'al-Lami' fi A'yan al-Qarn at-Tasi,' there are 11,691 characters written, and 1,075 female characters included. Out of 1,075, 411 female clerics have a relatively high religious education. Many local traditions in Indonesia promote a balance between women and men. For example, in the concept of Ambu, Nyi Pohaci, and pikukuh (rules) are a balance that can neutralize male power in the tradition of patriarchal society. And the categories of female ulama according to PPIM are campus scholars including Rahmah El-Yunusiyah, Zakiah Darajat, Bararah Bared, Tuti Alawiyah, then Islamic boarding school scholars including Sholihah Wahid Hasyim, Hj. Chamamah, the three clerics of socio-religious organizations include Nyai Ahmad Dahlan and Aisyah Amini. The four tabligh scholars include Lutfiyah Sungkar and Rafiqoh Darto Wahab.

From these definitions, there is no specification stating that only men deserve to be scholars and women do not. If they are qualified and competent, women can become ulama and have the potential to be closer to society because they embrace other women who sometimes have a relationship with male ulama. In addition to the lack of acknowledgment of the existence and role of "women clerics," the lack of information and news about their existence and work is also one of the factors that make "women clerics" receive less recognition from the Muslim community. Azyumardi Azra pointed out that studies on "women clerics" are still scarce in Indonesia and other Muslim areas: Arabia, West Asia, North Africa, Africa, the Indian Subcontinent, and others. Although studies on women and gender continue to find momentum, attention is rarely given to female Ulama.

Indonesia's Woman Ulama

The contribution of Ulama Women is essential because Islam that has developed in Indonesia has not only become a belief system but has also developed into a governance system that has transformed into a kingdom or sultanate that uses Islam as an ideological basis. Islamization in Indonesia cannot be separated from the role of people who have contributed to spreading Islam. The emergence of female figures with various scientific backgrounds and activities has shown the role and role of Indonesian women in spurring and encouraging the development of Islam in Indonesia.

Jajat Burhanudin et al. (2002), in the book *Indonesian Women Ulama*, noted thirteen female ulama who were engaged in education, da'wah, politics, social affairs, Sufism (TaSAWuf), and other fields. Several categories are given to classify each female ulama's expertise, but the categorizations overlap. The first category is "campus scholars, which include Rahmah El-Yunusiyah, Zakiah Darajat, and Tutty Alawiyah. The second category is the "ulama" of the pesantren, which includes Sholihah A. Wahid Hasyim, Hajah Chamnah, Hajah Nonoh Hasanah, and Suryani Thahir. The third category is "ulama" of socio-religious organizations which include Nyai Ahmad Dahlan, Sholihah A. Wahid Hasyim, Tutty Alawiyah, Hadiyah Salim and Suryani Thahir. The fourth category is "social and political activist clerics" which include Hajjah Rangkyo Rasuna Said, Nyai Ahmad Dahlan, and Aisyah Amini. The fifth category is "tabligh scholars" including Lutfiah Sungkar and Rafiqah Darto Wahab. These Indonesian female clerics with different qualities and expertise have encouraged further reproduction of the process of the emergence of female clerics, socio-religious activists, and even political activists. Moreover, in addition to the names above, several other clerics are active in meeting places for many women in Jakarta, such as Yoyoh Yusroh (Lecturer and Da'wah Activist), Nani Handayani (Sharia Preacher and Consultant), Herlini Amran (Sharia Writer and Consultant), or Wirianingsih (Lecturer and Da'wah Activist).

The role of women ulama in Indonesia is also represented by the work of women's organizations in the religious community. Islamic women's organizations were born in line with the spirit of renewal among Islamic organizations. The birth of this Islamic women's organization and its parent organization realized the importance of women's involvement in the struggle and da'wah of Islam. Among the women's organizations founded before and after early independence were Aisyiyah, Syarikat Islam Women, Peristri, Muslimat NU, and Islamic Women. This underdevelopment becomes a bad portrait considering that women are part of the nation's pillars. The Arabic proverb says, *Al mar'ah `Imad al-Bilad. Idza shaluhat shaluha al-Bilad, wa idza Fasadat Fasada al-Bilad* (Women are the pillars of the state, if they are good, the state will be good, if they are damaged, the state will be destroyed). Thus, the position of women is vital because it is the beginning of all forms of good or bad attitudes and behavior.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses qualitative methods by making and observing works, books, academic research, videos, internet sources, and historical documents. The existing data is then analyzed using the explanatory analysis method where the logic of social phenomena is common sense by using historical, anthropological, and sociological approaches. This research tries to show the role model of women scholars so that women today can learn and imitate the activities and struggles of these women scholars so that many benefits are generated for the improvement of the ummah, especially women. The concept of women scholars, contributions, strategies carried out by these women scholars are presented. Then the supporting and inhibiting factors of women

scholars in preaching are also discussed so that they can be understood in depth.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile

Tengku Fakinah or known as Tengku Faki, was born in 1856 AD in the village of Lam Beunot, Mukim Lam Krak, VII Mukim Baet, Sagi XXII Mukim, Aceh Besar. She is the daughter of Tengku Datuk, or Tengku Asahan, who was an official during Sultan Alaidin Muhammad Daud Shah (1823-1836 AD). While his mother, Fatimah, was the daughter of the founder of the dayah, Tengku Cik Lam, where Tengku Chik Ditiro Muhammad Saman (1836-1891 AD) studied.

Education

Since childhood, Fakinah has learned from her parents; her mother taught Arabic script reading, teaching reading the Koran, and religious sciences in Malay. In addition, his mother also taught him to sew, weave, embroider and cook. He was also taught fiqh (Islamic law), Sufism, morals, history, interpretation, hadith, and others to deepen his religious knowledge by his father. Until then, Fakinah grew up to be an intelligent girl in the field of Islamic scholarship; that is why she was nicknamed Tengku Fakinah. Tengku Fakinah also had time to take military education before the outbreak of the Aceh War. During his military education, Tengku Fakinah met a man who would later become her husband. In 1872 AD, Tengku Fakinah was married to Tengku Ahmad or Tengku Aneuk Glee (d. 1873 AD), a young ulama figure who was also one of the descendants of the ulama in Aceh. After marriage, they both taught at Dayah Lam Pucok, which Tengku Fakinah's father founded before the Aceh war broke out. The presence of Tengku Fakinah in Dayah influenced the students who studied there. At first, only male students, then after Tengku Fakinah taught, many women joined in learning.

When the Dutch began their aggression against Aceh in 1873, Tengku Fakinah's husband fought on the Pantai Cermin battlefield, where the Dutch landed. In the battle, Tengku Fakinah's husband died; at that time, Tengku Faki was only 17. Finally, the pesantren education built by Fakinah and her husband had to be developed by Fakinah herself without her husband, Tengku Ahmad. After that, he also married Tengku Ibrahim. Tengku Fakinah, together with her husband, who is also a cleric, Tengku Ibrahim, went to Mecca in 1915 to perform Hajj and lived there for four years while continuing to study. In 1914 Tengku Fakinah wanted to fulfill the fifth pillar, namely, to go on a pilgrimage. Before he left, first look for his muhrim. Thus she married a man named Ibrahim, who was her third husband. In July 1915, he set out for the holy land of Mecca. In Mecca, he stayed at the Aceh waqf house, Jalan Kusya Syiah, managed by Syech Abdul Gani from Aceh Besar. After completing the pillars of Hajj, he still lived in Mecca to study and deepen his knowledge of Jurisprudence on Tengku Syech Muhammad Saad, who came from Peusangan. The lectures given by the teachers are carried out in the Grand Mosque of Mecca to their students.

“After three years in Mecca to deepen his knowledge, when entering his 4th year in Mecca, his husband, Ibrahim, died in Mecca. So in 1918, Tengku Fakinah returned to Aceh; upon arrival at Lam Krak, his students were greeted with great fanfare. Moreover, at that time, he led the Dayah/Pesantren, which had been abandoned so far, and developed all the knowledge required in Mecca for his students.”

While in the Middle East, he met many scholars. Then in 1918 returned to Aceh alone because her husband passed away to rahmatullah. With a strong determination, he led Dayah Lamdiran and carried out changes and reforms in the field of Dayah Education. While in Mecca, Tengku Fakinah met many Islamic leaders from Egypt, North Africa, and others. From his meetings with these figures, he believes that fighting an occupation is not only enough with weapons but also must be equipped with knowledge.

Among the female students who later became scholars and taught, namely;

- a. Tengku Fatimah Batee Linteung;
- b. Tengku Sa'idah Lamjame
- c. Tengku Fatimah Ulee Tutue;
- d. Tengku Hawa Lamdilip.

Socio-Cultural Conditions and Conditions of Da'wah in her lifetime Aceh and Women di Aceh

In the Indonesian context, Aceh has been known as a stronghold of the Muslim community, with a majority Muslim population and a strong background of the political influence of Islamic power/kingdom on its history, culture, and traditions. This area has also been recognized as one of the centers of Islamic scholarship for the Indo-Malay archipelago, especially during the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, through intellectual networks between local ulama and haramin in the Middle East.

Although Islam is understood to support patrilineal values, some ethnic groups in Indonesia, such as Aceh, are indeed matrilineal societies. It also applies to other Muslim communities in Indonesia, such as the Minangkabau. In his work, Siegel (1969) mentions that Acehnese society is a matrifocal society with the dominant role of women, especially in the family, which has led to the 'marginalization of men in the household. Focused, but also implies two constructs: (1) a kinship system in which (a) the mother's role is structurally, culturally, and effectively central and (b) this multidimensional centrality is legitimate; and (2) societies in which these traits coexist, where (a) the relationship between sex is relatively egalitarian and (b) women and men are important actors in the economic sector. The practice and meaning of matrilocality are different from the 'female head of household' (female Head of household) as countries use to refer to in their policies and demographic data. The Head of household is almost always understood as male in state policy.

Only in the exceptional cases of widowed families are women considered heads of households. The matrifocal tradition does not reflect the particular case of a widow's family. The relative power of women can be achieved with or without the presence of a husband or other male clan. Outside

of state affairs or the need for official documents, people in Aceh rarely identify a head of household, mainly since sometimes more than one nuclear family inhabits the house. The facts show that women, especially the older ones, used to have relative 'power' and social bargaining power within this family structure. Historically, the glory of the Aceh kingdom was marked as a center of trade, education, and Islamic civilization in Southeast Asia, so several well-known scholars emerged. The role of Acehnese women in society since the royal period (Peureulak, Samudra Pasai, and Aceh Darussalam) during the war of independence is a unique phenomenon that has almost no equivalent elsewhere. At that time, Acehnese women could play a significant role until they became sultans, legislators, and role commanders, so there were no gender differences.

Aceh has various races in one culture. Uncompromising but friendly courageous spirits and religious fanaticism internalized in their souls make religion and self-esteem for them above all others. That is why the Dutch colonial assigned them the title "crazy" (pungo). This trait is not only possessed by men but also by women. Behind the subtlety and storage of Acehnese women, there is a spirit of steel as possessed by men. For Acehnese women, taking up arms and leading the war against them is not strange. H.C. Zentgraaff depicts Acehnese women in one short sentence as *de leidster het verzet* (leader of resistance) and *grandes dames* (big women). Acehnese women are described as brave and brave patriots who struggle with body and soul. The patriotism of Acehnese women is referred to as a physical manifestation of a character who does not know how to give up. They even surpass the Acehnese men, who are already known as men who are brave and not afraid to die in defending the ideals of their nation and religion.

Acehnese women held supreme power as queens in the early 15th century and from the mid to late 17th century. Recognition of women's rights to play a role in the highest political decision-making in the past, in the active construction of nationalism against European colonialists, had become a discourse weapon in the hands of Acehnese women then. Besides Tengku Fakinah, several Acehnese heroes include Cut Nyak Dhien, Admiral Malahayati, Cut Meutia, Pocut Baren, and others. Acehnese women can use this political situation to maintain their power in the long term. As stated in the 17th century, *Sabil War Tale* consistently supports equal opportunities for men and women to defend their country. "Whether it is a woman or a man, all of them, young and old, old age, childhood, according to *ijma*, pious, wicked, pious, ignorant, all must participate, kings, people, *uleebalang*, must fight equally, Kafir who attack our country, we must fight here immediately, it is forbidden to run, we must fight. *fardhu ain* on us."

In addition to the question of women's involvement in the war, there is another that is closely related: that of women's involvement in society. As James Siegel points out in his study of Aceh, in the 1960s, men were on the periphery, and women occupied a central position in society, owning houses and rice fields. The wife, who is also called *po rumoh* in Acehnese (the owner of the house), welcomes her husband as a guest in the house, not as a master. Prof. A.

Hasjmy (1914-1998), The historian and leader of the Aceh Special Region Council of Ulama confirmed this by saying that "... in the past, the Islamic sultanate in Aceh treated men and women equally. The right of women to hold the reins of royalty in the palace was fully recognized. Under the laws of the Sultanate of Aceh Darussalam, the rights of men and women are equal. Likewise, their obligation was to defend and build the sultanate. These rights and obligations provide opportunities for Acehnese women from the Sultanate of Perlak, Samudera Pasai, and Aceh Darussalam to actively participate in the government and military.

Acehnese women also use oral traditions within their families to pass on information and values to their children and grandchildren. Their children and grandchildren receive a detailed history of Aceh and Acehnese male and female heroes, specifically in the form of stories, poems, and songs. And things like this they do not receive from school or textbooks. Zentgraaf (1874-1990), a Dutch scientist who is also a former journalist, was very impressed with the patriotism of Acehnese women who rose to fight against the battlefield, either side by side with men or as warlords. Zentgraaff reviews carefully in a very admirable view; he says that "no nation is so passionate and fanatical in facing enemies other than the Acehnese with its women who are far superior to all other nations in the courage to face death. Even in defending a position of social and religious importance, Acehnese women, both behind the scenes and openly, have led a resistance that is no less superior than men."

Aceh still has many female heroes. For example, Nurasyiah was the first queen in Aceh, Queen Safiatuddin, Putri Lindung Bulan, Tengku Fakinah, and Pocut Meuligo. Sari, in 'Women's Participation in Local Politics in Aceh' noted that there were 18 influential women in Aceh's history recorded from 1353-1920. With so many women of capacity recorded in Aceh's history, it is not surprising that, to this day, the spirit of the fighters flows in the blood of Acehnese women. It is coupled with the prolonged conflict that occurred in Aceh to shape the character of Acehnese women to be so strong. It can be said that every activity of an Acehnese woman, even though she is outside the home for the benefit of her people and religion, is still under the control of her husband. Even so, the freedom of Acehnese women is not fully enforced. The glory of controlling the country is also not entirely in the hands of women. Moreover, they remain under the dominion of men.

The Aceh War

The Aceh-Dutch War, or the abbreviated Aceh War, was the war of the Aceh Sultanate against the Dutch, starting in 1873 to 1904. The Aceh Sultanate surrendered in January 1904, but the Acehnese people's resistance to guerrilla warfare continued. On March 26, 1873, the Dutch declared war on Aceh and began firing cannon fire into the mainland of Aceh from the battleship Citadel van Antwerpen. The First Aceh War (1873-1874) was led by Teuku Panglima Polem Sri Imam Muda Mahmud Arifin, who was also famous for Cut Banta Panglima Polem VII (1845-1879), and Sultan Mahmud Syah (d. 1528 AD) against the Dutch led by Köhler. Köhler, with his 3000 soldiers, was broken,

where Köhler himself died on April 14, 1873. Ten days later, war raged everywhere. The biggest one was when reclaiming the Baiturrahman Grand Mosque, assisted by several groups of troops. There are in Peukan Aceh, Lambhuk, Lampu'uk, Peukan Bada, to Lambada, Krueng Raya. Several thousand people also came from Teunom, Pidie, Peusangan, and several other areas. The Second Aceh War (1874-1880), Dutch troops led by General Jan van Swieten (1807-1888). The Dutch succeeded in occupying the Sultan's Palace on January 26, 1874, and it became the center of the Dutch defense. On January 31, 1874, General Van Swieten announced that all of Aceh became part of the Kingdom of the Netherlands. When Sultan Machmud Shah died on January 26, 1874, he was succeeded by Tuanku Muhammad Dawood (1864-1939), who was crowned Sultan at the Indrapuri mosque. The first and second wars were total and frontal wars, where the government was still running well, although the capital city of the country moved to Keumala Dalam, Indrapuri, and other places. In the third war (1881-1896), the war was continued in a guerrilla manner, and the *fi sabilillah* war was waged, where the guerrilla warfare system was carried out until 1903. In this guerrilla war, the Acehese troops were under Teuku Umar (1854-1899) with the Polim Commander and the Sultan. In 1899, when there was a sudden attack on the part of Van der Dussen in Meulaboh, Teuku Umar died. However, Cut Nyak Dhien, the wife of Teuku Umar, later appeared as a guerrilla war commander. The fourth war (1896-1910) was a group and individual guerrilla war with resistance, raids, ambushes, and killings without command from the center of the sultanate government.

Under the leadership of Imeum Lungbata as the cleric and Teuku Lamnga's first husband Cut Nyak Dhien as the *ulee balang*, the oath of "compulsory sabil war" was born. The oath pronounced in Aceh Besar then gained sympathy from scholars from other regions. Then, Tengku Cik di Tiro appeared, who was lined up by the Acehese as the leader of the sabil war. Not alone, Tengku Tjhik di Tiro is also supported by his younger brother, Tengku Cik Pante Kulu. The saga of *prang Sabi*, a form of resistance literature, is always echoed to support this movement. Because the *Hikayat Prang Sabi* not only formed a mental resistance against the Dutch but also turned it into a political strategy. Imran Teuku Abdullah said many Acehese fighters went to war with pieces of the *Hikayat Prang Sabi* lyrics. The pieces of the lyrics are often found on the bodies of those who died.

Inspiration for the *Hikayat Prang Sabi* The spirit of *jihād fi sabilillah* first echoed after the defeat of the Acehese troops by the Dutch troops. *Prang Sabi* in Acehese or *Sabil War* in Indonesian has a similar meaning to 'Holy War' or a struggle in the way of Allah, namely *jihād fi sabilillah*. On January 24, 1873, the commander of the Dutch military, Lieutenant General Jan van Swieten, succeeded in occupying the palace of the Sultanate of Aceh. A year later, on March 16, 1874, Banda Aceh changed its name to Kutaradja. In Aceh's slumped condition, awareness emerged to unite among the ulama, *ulee balang*, and the people. After serving in the fields of education, religion, nation, and homeland on 8 Ramadan 1359 H/3 October 1933, educator, scholar, and great hero Tengku Fakinah died at his residence in the village of Beuha Mukim Lam Krak

at the age of 75 years. He was buried in the Dayah Application complex, Aceh Besar District.

The Dakwah Contribution of Tengku Fakinah

Islamic Boarding School/Dayah in Lam Krak

Building an Islamic Boarding School with Her First Husband (Tengku Aneuk Glee)

When he was an adult (around 1872), Tengku Fakinah married Tengku Ahmad from the Aneuk Glee area, Indrapuri. Because marriages in Aceh have a matrilineal pattern, in which the husband must reside in his wife's family home, Tengku Ahmad must also reside in his wife's village, Lam Beunot. The people of Lam Beunot call T. Fakinah's husband with complete respect, namely Tengku Aneuk Glee. In the village of Lam Beunot, Tengku Aneuk Glee then opened a dayah which his father-in-law, Tengku Datuk, funded and received full support from the people of Lam Beunot and Imuem Mukim Lamkrak. The dayah then developed rapidly, visited by many teenagers and young people who were not only from Aceh Besar but even from outside Aceh Besar to study. At first, only two people taught the dayah, namely Tengku Aneuk Glee and his wife (Tengku Fakinah); the male students were taught by Tengku Aneuk Glee, while Tengku Fakinah taught the female students. In addition to teaching religious lessons. T. Faki also gives lessons on skills such as sewing and filigree.

However, when there was the first Dutch expedition to Aceh (1873), Tengku Imam Lam Krak and Tengku Ahmad/Tengku Aneuk Glee tarot in the Mukim best troops defending the waterfront Mirror Beach Ulee Lheu commanded by the Polem commanders Nyak Banta and Rama Setia (1874) died in a war that blocked the pace of the Dutch colonialists in Aceh. Their marriage has only been going on for two years. Moreover, T. Fakinah became a widow at the age of 17 years. Even so, T. Faki persisted in developing his dayah and simultaneously fought against the Dutch.

Jihad With Second Husband (Tengku Nyak Badai)

After two years of widowhood, she was then married by Tengku Nyak Badai, a young scholar from Pidie. Her husband is a Dayah graduate of Tengku Cik Tanoh Abe and a classmate of Tengku Cik Di Tiro. They got married in 1876. For 20 years, they together commanded the people of Aceh to fight the colonists. Tengku Fakinah is known as an expert in making explosives. As said by Hj. Juariyah: "She took the explosives to the top of the mountain, then cooked them there...." In 1981 Tengku Cik Di Tiro, the Great Commander of the Aceh War, died, then followed by the death of Tengku Cik Abdul Wahab Tanoh Abe in 1894. Although there was no command from the Commander in Chief, many great leaders of the Aceh struggle had fallen. T. Faki and Tengku Nyak Bada'i remained steadfast in continuing the relay struggle of these scholars. He settled and moved from Lam Krak, Indrapuri, Keumala, Tangse, and even to Gayo. Guerrillas in the forest kept the Acehnese leaders from being captured by the Dutch. And Tengku Fakinah's husband, Tengku Nyak Bada'i died in 1896.

The Aceh war subsided in 1903. Finally, with input from General Panglima Polim in 1911, T. Fakinah came down the mountain and returned to Lam Krak to rebuild the legacy of her parents, who had long been neglected during the war. Tengku Fakinah is an Islamic religious educator. Before the Aceh War broke out, he had built a pesantren. After the war, the pesantren was resumed. Tengku Fakinah performed her role as a warlord, cleric, and Islamic educator well. In the war, he incarnated as a commander who was feared and respected by the enemy. When he returned from the war, he returned to his figure as a great scholar. He is trying to rebuild his Islamic education, which has been ravaged during the war.

In constructing this pesantren, many community parties voluntarily issue zakat and personal donations so that this development runs smoothly. After this dayah was established, many people came from all over Aceh, such as: all corners of the three sides of Aceh Besar, Meulaboh, Calang, East Aceh, Pidie, and Samalanga, especially widows and girls, to study the Koran to Lam Krak. Public sympathy for the Tengku Fakinah pesantren is tremendous, so this place is visited by many guests from outside the Lam Krak mukim every day. Likewise, many came to deliver social donations for living expenses for the dayah/Islamic boarding school students so that the students who studied there, apart from receiving food and assistance from their parents, also received assistance from the general public. Other forms of donations contributed by the community to the dayah/pesantren, such as the Koran and books needed for lessons. At that time, Fakinah's school was the only center for Islamic education led by women.

Going Hajj with Her Third Husband (Tengku Haji Ibrahim)

During his life, Tengku Fakinah married three times; her second husband was Tengku Nyak Badai, who was also a martyr against the invaders. In 1914 Tengku Fakinah wanted to fulfill the fifth pillar, namely, to go on a pilgrimage. Before he left, first look for his muhrim. Thus she married a man named Ibrahim, who was her third and last husband. T. Fakinah, with her husband Tengku Haji Ibrahim 1915 AD, went on the Hajj and settled for a while in Mecca. There she used the time to increase her knowledge, especially religious knowledge. In Mecca, she stayed at the Aceh waqf house, Kusya Shiah street, managed by Syech Abdul Gani, who came from Aceh Besar. After applying the pillars of Hajj, she resided in Mecca to study science and deepen his knowledge of jurisprudence under Tengku Syech Muhammad Saad, who came from Peusangan. At the same time, it is most likely that T. Faki also learned from Sheikh Ahmad Khatib Minangkabau (d. 1916), Sheikh Sayyid Bakri Syatta, and Sheikh Sayyid Ahmad Syatta. Lectures given by her teachers were conducted in the Grand Mosque of Mecca to her students.

After three years in Mecca to deepen her knowledge, when entering her 4th year in Mecca, her husband, T. Ibrahim, died in Mecca. So in 1918, Tengku Fakinah returned to Aceh; upon arrival at Lam Krak was greeted with great fanfare by her students, and it was at that time that she led the Dayah/Pesantren, which had been released so far and developed all the

knowledge required in Mecca to the students. Her student. She brought new inspiration and was even welcomed by Acehese ulama and ulubalang, such as Tuanku Raja Keumala and Tuanku Panglima Polim Muhammad Daud. With a strong determination, he led Dayah Lamdiran and made changes and reforms in the field of dayah education. The metropolitan nature of Dayah education during the sultanate (before the war) was an essential factor for the continuity of the educational tradition in Aceh during the Dutch rule. What is meant by the metropolitan concept here is that Dayah education does not depend on local resources alone, and tradition does not make it exclusive. Because Dayah education in Aceh does not stand alone, even in war, this education can be maintained with the migration of scholars to continue to develop the tradition of dayah education in other places that are not reached by war. Dayah had an essential role during the Aceh war against the Dutch. At this time, Dayah was a place of education, training, and barracks for the fighters. Likewise, after independence, Dayah became the primary reference for Islamic education. Many of the leaders who emerged and led Aceh later were Dayah alumni. Dayah is also an Islamic educational institution that plays a vital role in Acehese society.

However, the Dayah built by Tengku Fakinah has not developed until now. The mosque is currently surviving due to the community's need for a large mosque, so the land allotted for the mosque was moved to a more prominent place. The Aceh government has made the main mosque building (original building) a Cultural Conservation. Tengku Fakinah's activities currently still being maintained are the taklim assembly at the mosque and the TPA, where the teachers are only women. There are around 16 female Koranic teachers who continue to teach the children in the assembly. In domestic life, Tengku Fakinah is not blessed with children from her first, second, or third husband. However, he has hundreds of ideological children ready to continue his struggle.

Social Charity

After becoming a widow and still a teenager, T. Fakinah then formed a Social Charity Agency to donate her charity to the homeland of widows and other women to be part of the charity. The agency he founded received support from the Muslimat around Aceh Akbar, which later expanded to Pidie. Its membership is growing fast. Many women from various regions in Aceh joined. This section of the Social Charity Agency has become very active in collecting donations from the people through supplies in the form of rice and money. Apart from gathering supplies for war, the members who stayed on the premises were busy preparing food for people who came from outside, such as Pidie, Meureudu, Salamanga, Peusangan, and others, to help with the war and pouring lead for rifle bullets and all that work. Under the leadership of T. Fakinah. T. Fakinah was the Commander of the War against the Dutch attack. She did not want to stay at her residence, even going back and forth throughout the Aceh Besar triangle to carry out diplomacy, visiting the homes of prominent people and rich people to wait for zakat to help the Aceh war was raging.

Asking for financial support for war costs in order to expel the kaphe alias infidels from Tanah Rencong.

Sukey Fakinah (Kuta Women's Defense/Women's Fortress) / Inong Balee

When the enemy controlled Kuta Raja (Banda Aceh now), then the defense moved to Kuta to the city of Lam Bhouk, Pagar Aye (Lhung Bata), then in 1883, the defense could be controlled by the enemy. To anticipate this, Tengku Syech Saman, called Tengku Tjik Di Tiro, strengthened the defenses of Kuta Aneuk Galong, the former Kuta Panglima Polem Nyak Banta, which the Dutch had confiscated in 1878. Thus, the war leaders simultaneously established other kutakuta, such as Tengku Empee Trieng (Kuta Karang), Tengku Pante Kulu (Kuta Tuanku), and others. Meanwhile, in Lam Krak, four Kuta (Forts of Defense) were established under the Tengku Fakinah Command, each of which was led by a subordinate commander:

- 1) Kuta Lam Sayun, led by Tengku Pang M. Saleh.
- 2) Kuta Cot Garot, led by Tengku Pang Amat.
- 3) Kuta Cot Weue, led by Tengku Fakinah herself.
- 4) Kuta Bak Balee, led by Habib Lhong.

As for the men who built these kuta-kuta (Forts), except for Kuta Cot Weue, the work was carried out by women since the construction of fences, digging trenches, and setting mines were carried out by women themselves, supervised by the warlord Tengku Fakinah herself. With other female colleagues like:

- 1) Cutpo Fatimah Blang Preh,
- 2) Nyak Raniah from Lam Uriet,
- 3) Cutpo Hasbi,
- 4) Cutpo Nyak Cut, and
- 5) Cut Puteh.

Since the fall of the Inong Balee fortress, Tengku Fakinah has been moving from one fort to another. In this movement, he continued to teach on an emergency basis, even when he was based in Tangse and Gayo Lues. This guerrilla movement ended after there was an agreement by the ulama to regularly reduce the guerrilla movement following the capture of Sultan 'Alaiddin Muhammad Daud Syah. In connection with the decision of the ulema's deliberation, then in 1911, Tengku Fakinah descended the mountain. He returned to his hometown in the Lam Krak area and rebuilt the Dayah Lam Diran devastated during the war. Tengku Fakinah is assisted by his students, who both just returned from guerrilla.

Move to Tangse

After the fall of Seulimum, Tengku Fakinah fled to lammeulo (Cubok); at first, he lived in Tiro with Teuku Tjik in Tiro Mat Yeet, then moved to Tangse and at the same time built his residence in Blang Peuneuleun (Pucok Peuneuleun). This area is a stunning area and very fertile land, so this place is used as a village and at the same time opens agricultural land. All remaining property, gold, and weapons were transported to this new area, and in this

area, a dayah (college/pesantren) was also built where women recited the Qur'an. However, in 1899 this village was attacked by Dutch soldiers, Tengku Fakinah's house was ransacked, and some of Tengku Fakinah's gold was taken by the Dutch soldiers while he was released from the soldiers' encirclement. Since then, Tengku Fakinah no longer builds a kuta (fort), but only guerrillas base together Pocut lam gugob, the wife of Tuanku Hasyim Banta Sultan. Pocut Awan is the mother of Tengku Panglima Polem and, with other women who are still active in guerrilla following in her husband's footsteps wilderness, moving to the mountains of Pasai and Gayo Luas, as well as other places around the Fresh Sea, under the supervision of Tengku Nyak Mamat Peureulak. Even though Tengku Fakinah no longer holds the role of a warlord, he is still active in religious education, especially teaching women who participate in the guerrilla movement by moving around.

Return to Lam Krak After Teuku Panglima Polem, Muhammad Daud and Teuku Raja Keumala were subdued by Van Heutz. Then on May 21, 1910, at the request of Teuku Panglima Polem, for Tengku Fakinah to return to his hometown to re-open the deah/pesantren in Beuha (Lam Krak). Thus in 1911, Tengku Fakinah returned to Lam Krak and re-opened the Dayah/Pesantren, which was well received by the general public. Her success in uplifting religious learning for women led her to Mecca in 1918, and she stayed there to study religion for three years after performing the Hajj. When he went to Indonesia, his struggle continued by him until he breathed his last in 1938. His institute still exists in Indonesia but changed its name to the Hadjah Fakinah Islamic Religious Education Foundation.

Tengku Fakinah Mosque

Every Aceh struggle, there must be a mosque in it. Mosques function to foster strong spiritual and monotheistic values. A mosque is a central place for meetings and deliberation for the Aceh struggle and the development and civilization of the Acehnese people. Likewise, with Tengku Fakinah. In addition to building a fort for his struggle, T. Faki built a mosque to gather people to worship in the congregation, attend taklim assemblies, and consult for all community affairs, including the strategy for the struggle against the Dutch infidels.

A source said that this mosque was founded in 1915 by Tengku Fakinah and assisted by santriwan and santriwati, who recited the Koran in his dayah. The area of the Tengku Fakinah mosque is 15 x 15 meters. This building is located in Blang Miro Village, Simpang Tiga District, Aceh Besar Regency. Tengku Fakinah Mosque was built after Tengku Fakinah's return from the guerrilla war. Historical records inform that Dayah Lam Diran (Lam Krak - Sibreh) had developed under the leadership of Tengku Fakinah with her husband Tengku Ahmad long before the Dutch attacked. At a location near the mosque, a fort was erected, which was named Inong Balee (a widowed woman). This fort is a place for Tengku Fakinah and other warriors to gather to formulate a war strategy. But now, the fort is no longer visible; the building has been razed to the ground with age.

On June 9, 1896, the Dutch sent troops led by J. W. Stempoort to attack Kuta Inong Balee in Lam Krak. This attack took two months, proving the strength and tenacity of Tengku Fakinah's defense. In August 1896, Fort Inong Balee in Lam Krak could be occupied by the Dutch. Along with population growth, the mosque measuring 15 x 15 meters can no longer accommodate worshipers. So in 1983, the five daily congregational prayers and Friday prayers were moved to a new mosque, the At-Taqwa Mosque, which is located not far from the Tengku Fakinah mosque. However, the Tengku Fakinah mosque is still used as a place for recitation and meetings by the local community, until now. A few years later, the Al-Istiqamah Islamic Boarding School Tengku Chik Rangkang Manyang was founded at the mosque, whose students came from local villagers. The regional government of Aceh Besar, through the Department of Culture and Tourism, has designated the Tengku Fakinah mosque as one of the historic mosques. In addition to the value of historicity and religiosity, the determination of this mosque as a historical mosque is also due to its founder, who is a figure of a freedom fighter.

Ateung Seunabat

One of the results of his work with the community is a road called "Ateung Seunabat," which is quite long; until now, it is still known as "Ateung Tengku Faki" (Tengku Fakinah Street). Moreover, several places in Aceh use Tengku Fakinah as a street name. The educator, scholar, and great hero Tengku Fakinah died on October 3, 1933/8 Ramadan 1359 H at the age of 75 years. He was buried in the Dayah Lamdiran complex, Aceh Besar District. To perpetuate his extraordinary service in Banda Aceh, his name was used as the name of one of the hospitals in Banda Aceh.

The magnitude of the appreciation and respect of friends and foes for Tengku Fakinah as a hero and educator of women can be seen from the repeated visits of Dutch officials to Tengku Fakinah to her dayah, starting from the Governor, Residents, high-ranking officers, and other officials. In addition, she visits her friends, such as Tuanku Raja Keumala, Teuku Panglima Polem Muhammad Daud, and others. To perpetuate her excellent service in Banda Aceh, her name was used as the name of one of the hospitals in Banda Aceh. And a nursing academy was also founded under her name.

This Study Describes

First, the existence of these women scholars comes and grows with the support of people and environments that have a strong religious background, whether from father, mother, husband, teacher, or extended family who love religion. These women scholars do not stand alone, it is the supportive environment and social conditions that give them the opportunity to continue to develop in science and scholarship. Secondly, these women are not only armed with a strong desire but also financial support that cannot be said to be small. Whether it is obtained from her parents, her husband, or from the surrounding community. Because one of the supporting factors for the success of da'wah is the cost or sacrifice of the property owned. Third, da'wah and the process of learning about Islam and how to implement Islamic values have

always been carried out throughout her life. Women to be awarded and pinned the title of ulema is not because of a short and short path but through a long process, where at the time he lived the majority of women in Indonesia did not get a place in society, especially in the field of education. These women who later became scholars took a long time and struggled more painstakingly than ordinary people or male scholars so that they could become female scholars. Fourth, if carefully observed, the intelligence, managerial skills and creativity of these female scholars are categorized as beyond their time. So that they can exist in addition to raising the status of women, also spreading benefits including for men.

This is in accordance with the principle of demanding knowledge as expressed by Imam Syafii,

بَيَانُ تَفْصِيلِهَا عَنْ سَأْنِ بَيْتِكَ # بِسِنَّةٍ إِلَّا الْعِلْمَ تَنَالُ لَنْ أَخِي
زَمَانٌ وَطَوَّلُ أَسْتَاذٍ وَصُحْبَةٌ # وَبُلْغَةٌ وَاجْتِهَادٌ وَجِرْصٌ ذَكَاءٌ

"My brother, one does not acquire knowledge except by means of six things of which I will give details: intelligence, enthusiasm, earnestness, sufficiency, friendship (learning) with the ustadz (teacher), and taking a long time."

Because women can become scholars because of their struggle for knowledge, da'wah, and women. It is women who strive for the happiness of the afterlife who are ultimately known and remembered as scholars. Because they can use the opportunity of their life and devotion in the world for the hereafter. They not only understand the science of the hereafter but also understand the science of the world to support their ability to improve the order of human needs in general. However, the weariness of the world did not deceive them and make them desire worldly life and pleasures. Because they understand the interests of society and are sensitive to the public interest. They were like torches in their time. They were women who did not care about the opinions of the rulers nor did they care about the opinions of the people; these women showed the people what the Qur'an, as-Sunnah, and the scholars taught them.

CONCLUSIONS

The contribution of da'wah made by Indonesian female ulama Tengku Fakinah (d. 1933 AD) consists of various aspects. These women scholars are not only active in teaching in taklim assemblies, they give whatever they have for their da'wah. In addition to support from families and students and the community, they build da'wah facilities and facilities with the assets (in the form of goods, valuables, and money) they have. These scholars also give their energy and all their time for the betterment of the ummah, not only for women but also for men. Often they have to prioritize the benefit of the ummah over themselves. These women scholars are not only concerned with religious matters but also national and community affairs, education including the economy. They teach economic independence so that women can be independent and not depend on their husbands or parents. Because their goal is

the pleasure of Allah, the spread of Islam, the realization of maqashid sharia, and the benefit of the ummah.

The various strategies carried out by these female scholars in their da'wah still show the existence of their ulema like men, namely their presence which is a mercy (helping all groups that must be helped and fought for as long as it does not conflict with Islamic law, Islamic Izzah and Muslims). Diligent in worship, choosing a simple life (zuhud, detaching themselves from material / worldly measures and interests, having knowledge of the hereafter, religious knowledge in sufficient levels, understanding the benefits of society, sensitive to public interests, and devoting all their knowledge to Allah, the right intention in science and charity. In addition to building educational institutions aimed at their people, they also poured their thoughts in developing society both for their students but also for women to continue to increase their status in all lines of life, including writing and community organizations. So that these efforts produce and strengthen the social integration of society, help people who are lacking, encourage people to be able to make new breakthroughs in an effort to meet the needs of their lives, and foster an attitude of caring in people's lives. Likewise, the supporting and inhibiting factors for women clerics in their time in preaching are diverse. In every century there are changes that also show that every era there is a shift in the position of women in their society and it is greatly influenced by the culture and events that occurred at that time.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research is still needed on this topic "Tengku Fakinah (D. 1933) Indonesia's Woman Ulama."

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